

THE ROLE OF THE PSYCHOPEDAGOGUE AND INTERVENTION IN LEARNING DIFFICULTIES: REFLECTIONS AND PRACTICES

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to clarify the role of the psychopedagogue and intervention in learning difficulties in the educational process. In view of this, it aims to show the importance of psychopedagogical work in learning difficulties and in the development processes for learning paths in the school context. In this way, the following question arises: what is the importance and role of the psychopedagogue in the intervention of learning difficulties? In an attempt to answer the question in question, this qualitative and bibliographical research brings the theoretical contribution of important authors inherent to the theme. Among some, we can mention: Jean Piaget (1971), Vygotsky (2003), Bossa (1994, 2000), Freinet (2004) among others, who contributed to a reflection on aspects related to learning difficulties, as well as the importance and role of the psychopedagogue in the intervention to solve learning difficulties in the school environment or outside it. Finally, as a result of this study, it was realized that both institutional and clinical psychopedagogy plays an important role in solving learning difficulties.

Keywords: Psychopedagogue, Learning Difficulties, Psychopedagogical Practice, Psychopedagogical Interventions.

INTRODUCTION

This work aims to understand the role of the educational psychopedagogue and his/her practical relationship with students, in the intervention to try to solve learning difficulties .

Psychopedagogy is a science that studies the human learning process, and its object of study is the human being, in the process of constructing knowledge. The psychopedagogue has the function of observing and evaluating the true needs of the school and its desires, as well as verifying, together with the Political Pedagogical Project, how the school conducts the teaching-learning process, ensuring the success of its students and how the family exercises its role as a partner in this process (BOSSA, 1994).

It is important to emphasize that psychopedagogy is part of the institution with the objective of working preventively in the various situations involving teaching and learning difficulties and the bonds that can be established in the three areas: school, family and student. It is a fact that human beings are very complex and have skills, in order to develop their abilities, they need to live psychologically well in all areas, such as: cognitive, psychomotor, affective or social.

In this tripod of relationships: school, family and student, the individual creates a form of stimulus to express their emotional bond, which according to Piaget, he points out by saying:

Affective life, like intellectual life, is a continuous adaptation and the two adaptations are not only parallel, but interdependent, since feelings express the interests and values of actions, of which intelligence constitutes the structure. (PIAGET, 1971, p. 271).

According to Piaget, a person becomes a social individual through their interpersonal relationships in their daily lives over the years. And, considering that school is part of these relationships, it is responsible for a large part of the formation of the human being, therefore, the work of the psychopedagogue in this locus has a preventive and therapeutic character in the sense of seeking to create skills and abilities to solve problems.

For Bossa (2000), psychopedagogy is:

[...] a term that is distinguished in three connotations: as a practice, as a field of investigation of the act of learning and as scientific knowledge. Therefore, it is important to try to understand Psychopedagogy as an area that has, throughout its history, created its own theoretical body, systematizing instruments capable of carrying out its investigations, without proposing to specialize a professional by giving him part of what he lacks. (BOSSA, 2000, p.21).

This author clarifies that the process of socialization and learning, as well as the affective relationship, must be part of the other. In this, the individual in the social environment can create affective bonds built on the basis of interaction in the environment in which he or she is inserted. Thus, affection in school life establishes a bond of love between the learner and the teacher, but

the pedagogical practice in the classroom becomes an environment for learning values, attitudes, and affective relationships, but the teacher is the facilitator of this affection.

In this proposal, Vygotsky (2003) warns:

If we want students to remember better or exercise their thinking more, we must make the activities emotionally stimulating. Experience and research have shown that an event imbued with emotion is remembered more solidly, firmly and for a longer period of time than an indifferent event. Every time you communicate something to a student, try to affect his or her feelings. Emotion is no less important a tool than thought. (VYGOTSKY, 2003, p. 121).

Thus, affection must be present in the classroom or outside of it, but affective bonds develop the emotional aspects that develop the student's cognitive abilities. In this case, the student in his learning process in the school environment demonstrates various feelings that can help or harm, such as: insecurity, fear, sadness, anger, joy, anxiety, love, affection and trust that the student finds in the teacher.

At school, each student brings and presents his or her own baggage, each one different from the others, whether due to genetics, the environment in which they live, their desires and wishes. Difficulties at school can arise due to several factors, such as: the school itself, its culture, its policies, its teachers, the relationship between the teaching staff and students and the methodology applied.

In this sense, other factors that are outside the school environment also contribute to learning difficulties and can be: organic, emotional, cultural, intellectual, family and other more specific factors, such as dyslexia, dysgraphia, dyscalculia; these are considered disorders or disturbances, which must be properly diagnosed for the development of this student's learning.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology used in this research is qualitative in nature, which is concerned with the level of reality that cannot be quantified, that is, it works with the universe of meanings, motivations, aspirations, beliefs, values and attitudes (MINAYO, 2014).

In view of this, the following research problem arose: what is the importance and role of the psychopedagogue in the intervention of learning difficulties? To try to answer this question, we appropriated important authors related to the subject in question, such as: Jean Piaget (1971), Vygotsky (2003), (Bossa 1994, 2000), Freinet (2004) among others, who contributed to a reflection on aspects related to learning difficulties, as well as the importance

and role of the psychopedagogue in the intervention to resolve learning difficulties, mainly in the school environment.

In addition to the authors mentioned above, in this research we sought a solid base of references in the official academic repositories (dissertations, theses, articles, etc.) of renowned educational institutions, with the purpose of legitimizing what was explicit in this bibliographic work.

In this context, readings presented in a linear and continuous manner were analyzed and organized so that it would be possible to first understand the learning difficulties, then the school's performance and, finally, the understanding of the role of the psychopedagogue. Therefore, as this is a bibliographical research, there was no participation of people in this study, and, therefore, the data collected in this research comes from the sources mentioned above.

DEVELOPMENT

The importance of the work of the psychopedagogue is fundamental for the school environment or outside it; therefore, it is the role of this professional to have knowledge about the social reality of the student, his/her family and the society in which he/she is inserted. Therefore, psychopedagogy acts as a way of establishing a link between the school, the student, the student's family, the environment in which he/she is inserted, studies and, his/her barriers in the difficulties to learn better. It seeks to know, understand, analyze the environment and intervene spontaneously in the learning process, developing teaching techniques in a way that stimulates and facilitates this process in the case of students who suffer from some type of learning disorder.

The Role of the Psychopedagogue in Learning Difficulties

It is known that it is the role of the psychopedagogue to work in the educational and health fields, focusing on the learning process and its difficulties, based on different theoretical references and of an interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary nature, according to the Code of Ethics of Psychopedagogy of the Brazilian Association of Psychopedagogy, reformulated by the ABPp Council, management 2011/2013 and approved in a general assembly on 11/05/2011. The role of the Psychopedagogue has the following objectives according to the aforementioned Code:

- Promote learning, contributing to the processes of school and social inclusion;

- Understand and propose actions to address learning difficulties;
- Conduct scientific research in the field of psychopedagogy;
- Mediate conflicts related to learning processes.

To this end, one of the characteristics of the role of the psychopedagogue is preventive, whether clinical or educational. Helping, guiding and mainly correctly diagnosing problems related to learning, thus avoiding school failure and errors in psychopedagogical intervention or diagnosis. The role of the psychopedagogue has been expanding more and more throughout the world, each country, however, with its own reality, taking this into account. In the case of countries surrounding Brazil, we can highlight that in Argentina, according to Souza et al. (2015), the investigation process begins with interviews with parents, with the aim of knowing the history of their student's life. From there, interviews are conducted with teachers to gather information about the teaching-learning process.

According to Silva et al. (2015), the psychopedagogue can work in clinical, institutional, hospital and business areas. In the clinical area, the psychopedagogue works individually in an office. He schedules the first interview with the parents and the child, if this is possible.

The patient uses instruments that characterize the psychopedagogical assessment, such as: games, toys, drawings, Piagetian tests and pedagogical activities. The patient takes notes of what is said and the behavior of those involved. Often, the patient detects that the complaints are related to the family or school context and not directly to the individual who apparently has a disorder and, if there is a disorder, the patient should be referred to the appropriate health area, psychologist, speech therapist, etc.

For the authors cited above: the institutional psychopedagogue works directly in schools, must work in partnership and know the school, teachers, management, coordinators, community very well, in short, everyone involved in the teaching-learning process, and especially the students who are part of this school, starting the process of his work with the student himself, not forgetting to present feedback to everyone involved in this process after the process has unfolded.

The institutional psychopedagogue must adopt an advisory role, observing, understanding and monitoring all school practices, the dynamics of the school and the classroom together with the teacher, and what is produced by the students, not restricting himself to diagnosis, but also intervening, making the appropriate referrals, when necessary, to psychologists, speech therapists, doctors, counselors, among others. He must also encourage the participation of the family and have a welcoming attitude towards all the actors in the learning process.

In this context, the psychopedagogue can work, in addition to the educational area, also in companies and hospitals, whose service refers to special education, in which there is psychopedagogical monitoring for children in special situations and conditions, both due to pathological factors and accidents that make them stay away from the classroom.

According to Silva et al. (2015), the psychopedagogue must first of all understand how the process of constructing written language and numbers occurs. After understanding this knowledge, he/she must delve deeper into the types of learning disorders and must know his/her field of activity, whether clinical, educational, hospital or business. It is also important that he/she is familiar with the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders. He/she must have the experience and sensitivity to perceive the human being and his/her relationship with teaching and learning, not forgetting the real definition of a given intervention, which is the level of suffering of the subject and the barriers and difficulties he/she encounters in his/her daily life, and only then can he/she provide the appropriate follow-up and referrals.

The role of the psychopedagogue encompasses the learning process as something inseparable from the family and school context, encompassing different foundations for solving difficulties in the learning context. Therefore, the importance of the psychopedagogue knowing how to deal with the student's difficulties in learning becomes a constant challenge, because it does not always find an answer in the teaching methodology or in school policy. Sometimes, such factors can go beyond the school walls and interfere with the student's concentration in such a way as to make him anxious and/or distracted. (BOSSA, 2000).

In this sense, if the school does not know how to respond to the student's distraction, the initial problem may become the beginning of others. The child begins to feel incapable of learning, and any unsuccessful attempt at an approach is met with aggression and indiscipline as a form of defiance towards the teacher (FAGALI, 2001). In this regard, the search for understanding by the professional who will contribute to the teaching and learning process is relevant in this research, since the great challenge for educational institutions today is to awaken motivation and the desire to learn in students.

According to Barbosa (2001):

"Transforming learning into pleasure does not mean carrying out an enjoyable activity, but rather discovering pleasure in the act of: constructing or deconstructing knowledge; transforming or expanding what is known; relating knowledge to each other and to life; being a co-author or author of knowledge; allowing oneself to experiment with hypotheses; starting from a context to decontextualization and vice versa; operating on existing knowledge; seeking knowledge from not knowing; sharing one's discoveries; integrating action,

emotion and cognition; using reflection on knowledge and reality; knowing history to create new possibilities." (BARBOSA, 2001, p. 53).

This may explain that learning goes beyond the pleasure of carrying out activities considered motivating. But to transform learning into motivating learning means socializing discoveries, interacting and sharing ideas, creating possibilities and perspectives in overcoming learning difficulties.

It is the role of the psychopedagogue to bring together parents, teachers and administrators to seek a way to try to solve the problem that interferes with the student's performance. In practice, collaboration generally becomes unfeasible due to conflicts of interest, agenda and instrumental impossibility (SMITH & STRICK, 2001).

For Smith and Strick (2000), the work of the psychopedagogue ends up becoming challenging as their aim becomes to investigate methodologies and policies that enable inclusion, discourage discrimination and build systematic adaptations in the search for inclusion and equity.

Difficulties in learning are not only linked to some physical or even mental deficiency. Emotional factors have been shown to be of great importance in aversive reactions to the act of learning (FAGALI, 2001). To this end, the psychopedagogue will act to restore the student's autonomy, providing them with means that are favorable to their development, in a positive way to restore self-esteem and lead the student to face their difficulties with appropriate strategies.

In addition to the work of the psychopedagogue, it is understood that the family has an important role in the student's development, because it will contribute to the first necessary learnings being carried out, and a good family relationship favors the educational process, in this sense the family must contribute to monitoring the student's school life, having the responsibility of being present in their development and academic progress.

The Psychopedagogue and His Interventions in Learning

The psychopedagogue must be prepared to assist teachers by providing individual pedagogical support, in order to contribute to the understanding of problems that may arise in the classroom, allowing the teacher to see alternatives for action and apply other techniques that may lead to intervention.

Another important aspect of the psychopedagogue in the intervention to solve learning difficulties is joint participation in parent meetings, clarifying, together with teachers, the

development of children; in class councils, evaluating the methodological process; in the school as a whole and monitoring the teacher-student relationship.

Bossa (1994) clarifies that:

[...] it is up to the psychopedagogue to perceive possible disturbances in the learning process, participate in the dynamics of the educational community, favoring integration, promoting methodological guidelines according to the characteristics and particularities of the individuals in the group, carrying out guidance processes. (BOSSA, 1994, p. 23).

It is important to understand that psychopedagogy achieves its objectives when, by expanding the understanding of the characteristics and learning needs of a given student, it opens up space for the school to make resources available to meet learning needs.

For Silva (2022), the psychopedagogue must analyze the Pedagogical Political Project (PPP), especially its teaching proposals and what is valued as learning. In this way, the psychopedagogical practice is transformed and can become a powerful tool in aiding learning. In this aspect, the interaction between the teacher and the student is essential for learning, and the teacher achieves this harmony by taking into account the knowledge of the children, the result of their environment (FREINET, 2002).

Silva (2022) also considers that learning difficulties are a topic that must be studied, taking into account all spheres in which the individual participates (family, school, society, etc.). It is known that there is never a single cause for school failure and that a student with learning difficulties is not a student who has a mental disability or related disorders. In fact, there are fundamental aspects that need to be worked on to obtain better performance at all levels of learning and knowledge.

Therefore, the partnership between school and psychopedagogue becomes essential in identifying cases that require specialized therapeutic care. Sometimes, with some interventions performed at the right time, it becomes possible to modify a situation that, otherwise, could become something more serious. (NASCIMENTO, 2013). The psychopedagogue has a very important role in taking care of all the learning processes that take place within the school. This means taking into account the learning processes of teachers and students, their fears, prejudices, difficulties and strengths that, articulated as a whole, portray the identity of the entire school group (BASSEDAS, 1996, apud SILVA, 2012, page 04).

According to Law 557, of December 4, 2013: Psychopedagogy in the public school system is now a Federal Law.

Law 557, of December 4, 2013, establishes the mandatory inclusion of a psychopedagogue and a psychologist in the team of specialists in public schools. As it is federal in scope, it applies to all public schools in the country.

The project reflects the importance of the psychopedagogue in the school environment, together with the psychologist, who can act intensively in the face of students' difficulties and disorders. The first paragraph of the text establishes that the work must be in basic education (elementary) - therefore, without contemplating, for now, early childhood education, secondary education and university level.

Psychopedagogical care is essential at all stages of the learning process. For this reason, ABPp (Brazilian Association of Psychopedagogy), together with other professional associations, continues to fight for the expansion of the Law, even recognizing the first advances.

The original text also specifies the way psychopedagogues work within institutions: individual and group care, focused on the personal, pedagogical, social and family context. Hiring is done through a public selection process, but the law does not specify whether this should occur with both professionals, psychologists and psychopedagogues, at the same time.

Therefore, psychopedagogical intervention is not presented as (re)educational, but rather as therapeutic (a therapy focused on learning); it is not aimed at a specific audience, because we are all learners, humans: children, young people, or the elderly who remain alive and active, while we learn and teach, we can contribute with our patent to the evolution of humanity. It is possible to see that psychopedagogy also has an important role in a new educational moment that is the insertion and maintenance of students with special educational needs (SEN) in regular education, commonly called inclusion.

For Nascimento (2013), the psychopedagogue in a school institution can develop several tasks, such as: helping teachers in the elaboration of lesson plans, aiming at improving understanding on the part of students; corroborating the construction of the institution's pedagogical project; guiding teachers in the most effective help to any student who presents some learning difficulty in the classroom; carrying out institutional diagnosis, minimizing pedagogical problems that are or will arise to harm the teaching-learning process of students.

In this sense, all psychopedagogical interventions must emphasize and work on the individual's emotional dimension through the establishment of bonds, acceptance and the constant search for pleasurable experiences. The intervention must provide a welcoming environment that promotes the patient's well-being. This will favor the construction and

strengthening of the individual's identity and self-esteem, preventing them from being reduced to the development of their intellectuality or their learning problems.

It is important to emphasize that affectivity is a dimension present in both the student and the psychopedagogue, that is, in a therapeutic process both parties are mutually affected. In the intervention, the psychopedagogue is responsible for taking care of what emanates and presents itself emotionally to the patient, who will naturally be infected by what he or she experiences. In the same way, one must be sensitively attentive to the bodily signs that indicate how the individual is experiencing the proposed interventions.

Wallon contributes to psychopedagogy when he interprets the notion of subject as a collection of social and physiological influences. According to Moraes & Oncalla (2011, p.215), the French author understands that "the individual is genetically social, humanized and individualized in relationships with other individuals". The organic and social aspects to be considered by the psychopedagogue in his/her interventions require a broader view and attention to the complexity of the subject and his/her contextualization. Therefore, a second indispensable function for care is to have knowledge of the environment in which the subject participates and interacts. It is also extremely important to qualitatively evaluate the relationships experienced, the possibilities offered, the life history and the daily activities that are part of the constitution of the individual to be cared for.

The Importance of the Psychopedagogue's Work: Reflections and Practices

The importance of the work of the psychopedagogue is fundamental for the school environment or outside it; therefore, it is the role of this professional to have knowledge about the social reality of the student, his/her family and the society in which he/she is inserted. Therefore, psychopedagogy acts as a way of establishing a link between the school, the student, the student's family and the environment in which he/she lives. It seeks to know, understand, analyze the environment and intervene spontaneously in the learning process, developing teaching techniques in a way that stimulates and facilitates this process in the case of students who suffer from some type of learning disorder.

To reflect on the work and practice of the psychopedagogue, it is important to quote Bossa (2000), who explains that psychopedagogy can be carried out at different levels. First, the psychopedagogue works in educational processes with the aim of reducing the frequency of learning problems. His/her work focuses on didactic-methodological issues, as well as the training and guidance of teachers, in addition to providing counseling to parents. In the second

role, the objective is to reduce and treat learning problems that have already occurred. To this end, a diagnostic plan is created, from which the curricula are evaluated with the teachers, so that the disorder does not recur, preventing the emergence of others.

In this regard, psychopedagogical practice in schools should be preventive and advisory work in the school context. According to Bossa (2000), "thinking about schools in the light of psychopedagogy means analyzing a process that includes methodological, relational and sociocultural issues, encompassing the point of view of those who teach and those who learn, including the participation of the family and society". Therefore, it is essential to consider the relationships between school production and the real opportunities that society provides to the different social classes.

Nowadays, with access to ICTs, psychopedagogues are using these media resources to enhance their analyses, as a very valid instrument in the intervention they want to practice. However, it is also important to know how to provide the child and their family with an analysis in terms of what type of information is being offered, since an excess of information can harm this action, and it would not be appropriate, since the child would not be able to absorb everything that is offered to them in an exacerbated way by the media. Ultimately, this has become a concern, because parents need to filter what is important, separating all information that is not necessary so that the child does not fall victim to unnecessary knowledge. This is also a concern of the psychopedagogue, because in essence, he or she is concerned with the learning process in general.

For Bossa (2007), this educational universe of the student can be worked on, saying that:

Clinical psychopedagogy seeks to understand in a global and integrated way the cognitive, emotional, social, cultural, organic, and pedagogical processes that interfere in learning, in order to enable situations that rescue the pleasure of learning in its entirety. Including the promotion of integration between parents, teachers, educational counselors and other specialists who move in the student's educational universe. (BOSSA, 2007, p. 67).

The author makes it clear that this integration of educators, psychopedagogues and family (in this case, mainly parents) will provide the student with better conditions for learning. Therefore, it is necessary to reflect on and practice these elucidated principles.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

This research aimed to understand the role of the educational psychopedagogue and his/her practical relationship with students, in the intervention to try to solve learning difficulties.

Given the explicit approach in this article, it was noted how important the role of institutional psychopedagogy is as an investigator of the causes and difficulties in/of students' learning. For the problems that cause learning difficulties, it is the duty of institutional psychopedagogy to contribute to the process of reflection-action and reflection on the school context, guiding teachers to reformulate their school practices to improve learning.

It was observed that, in clinical psychopedagogy, the daily routine is still restricted, given the distance that separates the office from the school. However, psychopedagogy must be in partnership with the school, as long as both provide this dialogue. Psychopedagogy must always be focused on the perspective of the student, who has some learning difficulty.

When it comes to institutional psychopedagogy, it was possible to observe in this work the importance of the psychopedagogue in acting effectively within the school, with the purpose of working directly with students who need diagnosis, intervention, preventive/therapeutic actions and, mainly, with the intention of guiding teachers and families on the most positive solutions to assist in the learning of these students.

Thus, the relevant practice of the psychopedagogue in the school environment was also portrayed, which came to assist and present a parameter of important and necessary issues for education. In this way, elucidating important points that hinder students' learning.

Among so many psychopedagogical approaches, this research clarified that one of the important activities of the Psychopedagogue when receiving information about a student who has learning difficulties is to conduct a psychopedagogical assessment and prepare a report so that one can have a reliable demonstration of the social, psychological and educational issues of this student, so that from there they can define and work on targeted activities that can collaborate on the issues in which they present greater difficulties. In view of this, it is concluded that the Psychopedagogue needs to be in constant dialogue with the teachers who work with the student on a daily basis, so that he or she can assist within the individual needs of these learners.

It was noted that the clinical psychopedagogue is a licensed professional prepared to assist children and adolescents with learning difficulties. The work of this professional can be preventive or interventional (evaluation, diagnosis and intervention). When carrying out the

diagnostic process, the professional seeks to understand perceptions, sometimes implicit, about the reasons that lead patients to obtain unsatisfactory results in the face of the effort made in the search for learning.

It has become clear that it is the practice of professionals trained in clinical psychopedagogy to dedicate themselves to identifying the causes and learning problems by using the main resources of psychopedagogy, such as: Operational tests (Piaget), projective tests (drawings), EOCA (Learning-Centered Interview), anamnesis (interview carried out with family members to find out about the patient's life history), playful sessions, always with an attentive look and listening to everything and all of the patient's movements.

Finally, it became clear that the work of the psychopedagogue in its extension encompasses a wide range, leading him to perform his functions in three dimensions: individual clinical, group and institutional. The institutional area is not limited to schools, but also universities, companies and hospitals. In this way, psychopedagogical work is not restricted to just providing assistance with the problem, but also to prevention and health promotion, that is, it develops activities with teachers, students, hospitalized individuals or in similar institutions to try to avoid some learning difficulty in general.

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